

Looking Forward:

Bridging Infrastructures for
Equitable COVID-19 Testing
and Vaccinations

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Looking Forward:

Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations

Executive Summary

The second year of the COVID-19 pandemic has been shaped in part by our remarkable accomplishments, including rapid development of technologies to fight this devastating disease. With new tests, treatments, vaccines, and personal protective equipment, we have many more ways to combat COVID-19 today than when the pandemic started. However, **how** we work together to organize, lead, treat, and communicate with each other to use these technologies in communities experiencing the greatest impact is just as

critical as the extraordinary technologies themselves. We are our greatest resource to help keep our communities healthy and safe.

To increase access to testing and vaccinations, healthcare system leaders have designed and implemented new procedures, modified strategies, developed policies, and transformed environments. Healthcare workers quickly adapted their routines to care for patients with

COVID-19. Policy makers instituted stay-at-home orders and implemented mitigation strategies such as masking and distancing to slow the spread of the disease. Teams of scientists created safe, effective vaccines in record time. But the unsung heroes of the COVID-19 pandemic are the community members and leaders who worked tirelessly and quickly to build on their existing, trusted relationships to care for the most vulnerable in their communities.

For example, the Navajo Nation ([p. 34](#)) proactively instituted policies to increase testing and reduce transmission through curfew orders. Tribal leaders used existing networks and on-the-ground efforts to distribute food, masks, and other essential items to elders and other community members. School leaders across the country worked to find ways to open facilities safely ([p. 18](#)). Community partners in Pitt County, North Carolina, Chattanooga, Tennessee, and Ann Arbor, Michigan, rallied to distribute at-home testing kits in their communities ([p. 16](#)).

These and countless other examples of efforts to improve existing infrastructures are described in this Data Profile. Despite many obstacles, communities across the country continue to collaborate and to care for those hit hardest by the pandemic, using innovative solutions to keep their communities safe from COVID-19. Their work may help ease the burden of COVID-19 and build long-term structures that lead to healthier, more equitable communities. To do so, multilevel changes are needed in how we communicate, plan, and seamlessly connect across various groups

When we refer to those hit hardest by the pandemic, we mean the Black, Latinx, and Indigenous communities fighting the virus—but there are other groups that intersect by race, ethnicity, gender, geography, and socioeconomic status. They include:

- people living in congregate housing
- people with disabilities
- women who are pregnant
- children
- Black/African American people
- Hispanic/Latinx people
- American Indians/Alaska Natives
- Asians
- Native Hawaiians and other Pacific Islanders
- socioeconomically disadvantaged populations
- underserved rural populations
- sexual and gender minorities
- people with precarious legal status in the United States
- people with limited English proficiency or low literacy
- people who are homeless
- people who are victims of abuse or persecution
- people with multiple risk factors such as social isolation, mental illness, and substance use

and populations. We must transform our approaches for collective understanding and impact. This Data Profile and the COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy are meant to provide a starting point for discussing these ideas and making lasting change in pursuit of a healthier future for all.

An Evidence Academy is an engaged approach to understanding the state of the science, or the current evidence of COVID-19 testing and related factors in the populations most impacted by a problem. **Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations** is the second of these events hosted by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) [Rapid Acceleration in Diagnostics—Underserved Populations](#) (RADx-UP) initiative.

This Data Profile, which complements the second COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy, provides a brief snapshot of some of the public health infrastructures related to COVID-19 testing and vaccinations. These include, but are not limited to, infrastructures to support telemedicine, a pandemic-ready healthcare workforce, off-site testing centers, equitable contact tracing systems, community-specific communication frameworks, and equitable approaches to data collection and data sharing.

Since the first RADx-UP Data Profile and Evidence Academy in February 2021, testing remains an essential tool. Innovations in testing, vaccinations, and communications emerged as SARS-CoV-2 mutated into more contagious variants and hit communities that previously did not see many cases. Healthcare workers were beginning to get vaccinated at the time of our last Evidence Academy. Since then, almost every adult in the United States has had access to vaccination, but uptake is not universal as fear, distrust, and misinformation remain. Given the persistence of the pandemic and the rapidly changing pace of technologies and practical solutions in communities, we are holding the second Evidence Academy in November 2021, recognizing the importance of vaccination, while focusing on the mission of advancing testing technologies.

As you read this Data Profile, we encourage you to keep in sight the people behind the evidence. They include the people we have saved and those we have lost in the COVID-19 pandemic. They also include community leaders advocating for policies, neighbors helping neighbors, and researchers and healthcare professionals.

The COVID-19 crisis continues. We need to identify strategies for using available tools and methods to keep fighting this pandemic. Most importantly, we need to keep supporting each other and expressing gratitude for the countless champions among us. We hope you find this Data Profile a useful guide to appreciating the massive effort—from laboratory research to conversations with neighbors—that has yielded so many ways for us to work together.

This Data Profile includes:

- **A list of all projects** supported through the RADx-UP initiative, a network of 85 NIH-supported projects across the United States.
- **Literature summaries** examining the complexity of testing through the lens of the core themes, with emphasis on practical strategies and lessons learned. These summaries cover:
 - Policies to Support COVID-19 Surge and Routine Testing
 - Equity in Data Sharing
 - Pandemic Preparedness
 - Establishing Communication Frameworks
 - Strengthening Multi-Sector Partnerships
- **In-Context Perspectives** from RADx-UP community partners and researchers woven throughout the Data Profile.
- **Reference materials** on the types of COVID-19 tests and vaccines currently in use.
- **A glossary of common terms** used in testing, as well as other terms used in the Data Profile.

This compilation of information will ground attendees of this Evidence Academy in our ongoing series so that we begin our conversation with a common understanding of the ways we can work to bridge infrastructures. During the event, attendees will discuss these topics in the context of the communities they serve and will devise and share strategies for action.

We hope this document serves as an initial roadmap to guide us all toward a healthier future, one in which all communities have the best chance for good health.

About Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics– Underserved Populations (RADx-UP)

RADx-UP is an NIH-supported initiative aimed at ensuring that all residents of the United States have access to COVID-19 testing, with a focus on communities most affected by the pandemic. RADx-UP is developing strategies to reduce disparities in COVID-19 testing by supporting over 120* community-engaged projects across all US states and territories. These projects are seeking to understand and remove barriers to COVID-19 testing in their communities. They are studying COVID-19 testing patterns, data on

disparities in infection rates, and disease progression and outcomes.

RADx-UP is part of a larger NIH initiative to help speed innovation in the development and implementation of COVID-19 testing. There are three other programs: [RADxSM Tech](#); RADxSM Advanced Technology Platforms ([RADx-ATP](#)); and RADxSM Radical ([RADx-rad](#)).

Table 1: RADx-UP Projects and Recruitment Locations (N=85)[†]

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
The University of Alabama at Birmingham	A Dynamic COVID-19 Community-Engaged Testing Strategy in Alabama (COVID COMET)	Alabama
The University of Alabama at Birmingham	COVID-19 Testing Model Among Vulnerable Populations: From Community Engagement to Follow-Up	Alabama
Washington State University	Community Organizations for Natives: COVID-19 Epidemiology, Research, Testing, and Services (CONCERTS)	Alaska, Colorado, Kansas, Minnesota, New Mexico, Oklahoma, Washington
Brown University	IMPACT-C: Improving Vaccine Uptake In Skilled Nursing Facilities	All states and territories
Johns Hopkins University	LITE CONNECT: Addressing Testing Gaps and Epidemiologic Disparities of COVID-19 Among Transgender People in the United States	All states and territories
Northwestern University	Supporting COVID-19 Prevention and Testing for Marginalized and Minoritized Youth and Young Adults	All states and territories
Arizona State University, Tempe	A Survey Related to Eliminating COVID-19 disparities in Arizona in Partnership With Underserved/Vulnerable Communities	Arizona
Arizona State University, Tempe	Back to ECE Safely With SAGE: Reducing COVID-19 Transmission in Hispanic and Low-Income Preschoolers	Arizona
Johns Hopkins University	Protecting Native Families From COVID-19: Radx Initiative	Arizona, New Mexico
University of Arkansas for Medical Sciences	Community Based COVID-19 Testing Evaluation	Arkansas
The University of Chicago	Community Network Driven COVID-19 Testing Among Most Vulnerable Populations in the Central United States (C3)	Arkansas, Illinois, Indiana, Louisiana, Texas
University of California, Davis	ÓRALE COVID-19!: Organizaciones para reducir, avanzar y lograr Equidad contra el COVID-19 (Organizations to Reduce, and to Advance, and Lead for Equity Against COVID-19).	California

*This number includes the NIH-funded projects, the CDCC, as well as the projects supported by the RADx-UP CDCC through the Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Program and Rapid Research Pilot Program projects. [Learn more here.](#)

[†]Table 1 and Figures 1–3 represent data from NIH-supported RADx-UP projects as of July 2021. Data were collected from RADx-UP projects through an initial intake survey conducted during project onboarding.

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
University of California, San Diego	Harnessing Technological Innovation and Community-Engaged Implementation Science to Optimize COVID-19 Testing for Women and Children in Underserved Communities	California
University of Southern California	Use of Behavioral Economics in Repeat SARS-CoV-2 Antibody Testing in Disadvantaged Communities	California
San Diego State University	COMMUNITIES FIGHTING COVID!	California
University of California, San Francisco	Collaborative Community Networks to Optimize Implementation	California
University of California, San Diego	COVID-19 Testing in Underserved and Vulnerable Populations Receiving Care in San Diego Community Health Centers	California
Charles R. Drew University of Medicine and Science	A Community Health Worker Intervention to Identify and Decrease Barriers to Pre-Procedural COVID-19 Testing Among Los Angeles County Department of Health Safety-Net Patients	California
University of California, San Francisco	Getting Asian Americans INFORMED to Facilitate COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination	California
University of California, Los Angeles	Impact of COVID-19 Testing and Mitigation on Equitable Return-to-School in the Second Largest US School District	California
San Diego State University	Communities Fighting COVID!: Returning Our Kids Back to School Safely	California
Washington University in St. Louis	Using Health Communication to Increase COVID-19 Testing and Vaccination in Underserved Populations	Connecticut, Nebraska, North Carolina, Washington
Delaware State University	Social and Behavioral Implications for COVID-19 Testing in Delaware's Underserved Communities.	Delaware
Kennedy Krieger Institute	Supporting the Health and Well-Being of Children With Intellectual Developmental Disability During COVID-19 Pandemic	District of Columbia, Maryland, Missouri, Pennsylvania, Virginia
Howard University	Community Conversations About COVID-19	District of Columbia, Maryland, Virginia

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
Florida International University	Community-Engaged Research on COVID-19 Testing Among Underserved and/or Vulnerable Populations	Florida
University of South Florida	Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications (SEBI) Research on COVID-19 Testing and Vaccine Uptake among Rural Latino Migrants in Southwest Florida	Florida
University of Miami Miller School of Medicine	Maximizing Child Health and Learning Potential: How to Promote A School Culture of Safety in the Era of COVID-19	Florida
Yale University	COVID-19 Testing and Prevention in Correctional Settings	Florida, Minnesota, Rhode Island, Washington
Emory University	Rapid Optimization of COVID-19 Testing for People Affected by Diabetes	Georgia
Georgia State University	Increasing Representation of Black Communities in SARS-CoV-2 Serosurveys by Understanding Barriers and Motivations for Participation	Georgia
University of Hawai'i at Manoa	Puipua le Ola: Increasing Reach and Uptake of COVID-19 Testing among Pacific Islanders in Hawaii and Guam	Guam, Hawaii
University of Hawai'i at Manoa (Hedges)	Community Driven Approach to Mitigate COVID 19 Pacific Alliance Against COVID-19 (PAAC)	Hawaii
University of Hawai'i at Manoa	PAAC SARS-CoV-2 Antigen Testing in the Community Empowering Schools as Community Assets to Mitigate the Adverse Impacts of COVID-19	Hawaii
University of Illinois at Chicago	Investigating the Effectiveness of COVID-19 Testing Choices, Community Engagement, and Culturally-Embedded Health Literacy Delivery in a Medically-Underserved, Community-Based Sample	Illinois
Rush University Medical Center	Alive Church Network: Increasing COVID-19 Testing in Chicago's African American Testing Deserts	Illinois
Medical College of Wisconsin	Understanding the COVID-19, Racism, and Violence Syndemic and Its Effects on COVID-19 Testing Disparities	Illinois
Washington University in St. Louis, North County Schools	Assessing Testing Strategies for Safe Return to K-12 Schools in an Underserved Population	Illinois, Missouri

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
University of Kansas Medical Center	RADx-UP: Improving the Response of Local Urban and Rural Communities to Disparities in COVID-19 Testing	Kansas
LSU Pennington Biomedical Research Center	Transforming Community Engagement to Increase SARS-CoV-2 Testing in Underserved Populations in Baton Rouge (TESTUP-BR)	Louisiana
Xavier University of Louisiana	Assessing Vaccine Hesitancy and a Pharmacist Led Intervention Model to Increase COVID-19 Vaccine Uptake Among African Americans	Louisiana
Johns Hopkins University	The Johns Hopkins Center for AIDS Research (JHU CFAR) RADx-UP	Maryland
Johns Hopkins University	COVID-19 Response for the Latino Community	Maryland
Johns Hopkins University	Exploring Barriers and Facilitators to Women Who Use Drugs (WWUD) Awareness, Acceptance and Uptake of COVID-19 Testing (CARE Study)	Maryland
Johns Hopkins University	Community-enraged viral testing strategies to promote return to in-person school in Baltimore City Public School—Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Factors in the Return to School Among Underserved Communities in Maryland	Maryland
Washington University in St. Louis	Children With Intellectual and Developmental Disability (IDD) during COVID	Maryland, Missouri
Harvard School of Public Health	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics—Underserved Populations COVID-19 Needs Assessment	Massachusetts
University of Missouri-Kansas City	COVID-19 Testing and Linkage to Care With African American Church and Health Agency Partners	Missouri
Washington University in St. Louis	Safety, Testing/Transmission, and Outcomes in Pregnancy with COVID-19 (STOP-COVID-19 study)	Missouri
ICF Macro, Inc.	NIH RADx-UP COVID-19 Testing, Learning, and Consultation (School TLC) Study: Phase 1 Test Preference Study	Missouri
Montana State University	Protecting Our Community: A Pragmatic Randomized Trial of Home-Based COVID Testing with American Indian and Latino Communities	Montana, Washington
Johns Hopkins University	Project Safe Schools: Re-opening schools SAFELY for Native American Youth	Navajo Nation (northeastern Arizona, northwestern New Mexico, southeastern Utah), White Mountain Apache Tribe (northeastern Arizona)

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
University of Nebraska Medical Center	Mobile Health-Targeted SARS-CoV-2 Testing and Community Interventions to Maximize Migrant Children's School Attendance During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Nebraska
Rutgers Biomedical and Health Sciences	New Jersey Healthcare Essential Worker Outreach and Education Study - Testing Overlooked Occupations (NJ HEROES TOO)	New Jersey
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	Optimization of a New Adaptive Intervention to Increase COVID-19 Testing Among People at High Risk in an Urban Community	New Jersey
University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center	Keeping Rural Minority 'Essential' Workplaces Open Safely During The COVID-19 Pandemic: The Role of Frequent Point-of-Care Molecular Workplace Surveillance for Miners	New Mexico, Wyoming
New York University	A Nurse-Community Health Worker-Family Partnership Model to Increase COVID-19 Testing in Urban Underserved Communities	New York
New York University	Rapid Acceleration of Acceptable COVID Testing and Care Options for NYC Public Housing Residents	New York
Columbia University	Reaching Communities Through the Design of Information Visualizations (ReDIVis) Toolbox for COVID-19 Results	New York
New York State Psychiatric Institute	Leveraging Social Networks to Increase COVID-19 Testing Uptake: A Comparison of Credible Messenger and Chain Referral Recruitment Approaches	New York
New York University	Project pErception of coVID tEsting aNd vaCcinE (EVIDENCE)	New York
University of Rochester	COV-IDD: Testing For COVID-19 In High-Risk Children with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities	New York
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	Adapting Community-Based Task-Shifting for the COVID-19 Response Among Underserved Populations in Piedmont, North Carolina (ACT-UP)	North Carolina
North Carolina Central University	Building Resilience and Vital Equity (BRAVE)-Increasing COVID-19 Testing in American Indians	North Carolina
Duke University	COVID-19 Surveillance and Exposure Testing in School Communities	North Carolina
The Ohio State University	Improving Access to COVID Testing for All in Ohio (IMPACT-Ohio)	Ohio
Cherokee Nation	Cherokee Nation Community-Driven Program for Testing and Contact Tracing (Cherokee PROTECT)	Oklahoma
University of Oklahoma Health Science Center	Community-Engaged Approaches to Testing in Community and Healthcare Settings for Underserved Populations (CATCH-UP)	Oklahoma
University of Oregon	Scaling Up SARS-COV-2 Testing to Serve Latinx Communities	Oregon
University of Oregon	Creating a Sustainable Infrastructure for SARS-COV-2 Testing at Syringe Exchange Programs	Oregon
University of Pennsylvania	COVID-19 Self-Testing Through Rapid Network Distribution (C-STRAND)	Pennsylvania
Ponce Health Sciences University	Puerto Rico Syndromic Surveillance System COVID-19 Network (COVID19 PR Surveillance Network)	Puerto Rico
Yale University	Community-Engaged Research to Improve the COVID-19 Testing Cascade Among Underserved Populations in the US Caribbean Territories	Puerto Rico, U.S. Virgin Islands
Brown University	Developing A Realtime Monitoring System and Program to Improve COVID-19 Testing for Latinx Populations	Rhode Island
Massachusetts General Hospital	Understanding COVID-19 Testing Decisions in Great Plains American Indians	South Dakota
Stanford University	Monitoring COVID-19 and Building Capacity With Northern Plains Tribes and the Future of Pandemics	South Dakota

Project Institution	Project Title	Recruitment Locations
The University of Texas Health Science Center at Houston	Addressing COVID-19 Testing Disparities in Vulnerable Populations Using a Community Just in Time Adaptive Intervention - A UTHealth Center for Clinical and Translational Science Award Program	Texas
The University of Texas at El Paso	Implementing Community-Based Approaches to Increase SARS-CoV-2 Testing Among an Underserved and Vulnerable Hispanic Population	Texas
The University of Utah	SCALE-UP Utah	Utah
The University of Utah	SCALE-UP Counts: A Health Information Technology Approach to Increasing COVID-19 Testing in Elementary and Middle Schools Serving Disadvantaged Communities	Utah
Eastern Virginia Medical School	Effective Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Outreach and Guidance in Hampton Roads Public Housing	Virginia
University of Washington	Using Covid-19 Testing and Risk Communication Strategies To Accelerate Students' Return To School	Washington
West Virginia University	West Virginia Clinical and Translational Science Institute: Developing Novel Strategies to Increase COVID-19 Testing Among Underserved and Vulnerable Populations In West Virginia Through Community and State Partnerships	West Virginia
Medical College of Wisconsin	FightCOVIDMKE	Wisconsin
University of Wisconsin	ReSET: Restarting Safe Education and Testing for Children with Medical Complexity	Wisconsin

Figure 1: Map of RADx-UP Projects

Figure 2: Communities Served by RADx-UP Projects

NUMBER OF PROJECTS

Figure 2 shows the distribution of RADx-UP projects (N=85) across communities served. Approximately 67 percent of the projects are serving Hispanic or Latinx communities, and 59 percent are serving Black or African American communities. American Indian and Alaska Native communities are represented in a quarter of the projects. Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander communities account for 14 percent of the projects. Asian communities make up 27 percent of the projects. Children and older adults are each represented in 39 percent of the projects. Pregnant women are represented in 21 percent of the projects.

Figure 3: Settings Served by RADx-UP Projects

NUMBER OF PROJECT SETTINGS

Figure 3 shows the distribution of RADx-UP projects (N=85) across settings served. The highest proportion of projects serve community mental health centers at 42 percent. In-home settings are represented in 33 percent of the projects. Public housing settings are represented in 14 percent of the projects. Urban settings make up 35 percent of the projects and rural settings make up 31 percent of the projects. The needs of school settings make up 24 percent of the projects. Four projects focus on nursing home or long-term care facility settings, and one project focuses on prison or correctional facility settings.

[IN CONTEXT] Community-Engaged Researcher Perspective: John Foxe, PhD

RADx-UP Project: COV-IDD: Testing for COVID-19 in High-Risk Children With Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities, University of Rochester, New York

“You don’t want to introduce disease [COVID-19] into a school like ours [Mary Cariola Center], because it’s like a perfect incubator. Implications are much worse in a school like this than they would be in a school with neuro-typical kids. Multiply it by 10 when you’re talking about an intellectual and developmental disabilities (IDD) population. If one of these youngsters or staff has COVID,

there’s a very good likelihood that it would run through the school in short order.

“What do you do about that? Well, one thing, of course, is to test and to test often. Test symptomatic people to detect an occurrence of the virus as soon as it occurs and get that person out of circulation, get them isolated, get them treated so that it doesn’t get loose. The question then becomes, how much of that testing do you need to do? How do you do it? Where do you do it? Who does it? How quickly can you turn around the results? What kinds of tests do you need to do?

“If we [PCR] test on Monday, we have the [result] back first thing Tuesday morning. If there’s a positive test, we can prevent the child or staff member from coming to school. You need to be flexible and you need to be able to get around to do that. So, mobile testing units have been deployed to get out into the community and go where the kids are. You need to make

that as easy as possible, remove as many of the barriers as you can, be flexible, be mobile.

“If you could test everybody twice a day, the chances to pick up the very beginnings of a potential infection or outbreak would be very high, but it would be incredibly intensive work, intensive labor, intensively expensive. So, that’s not an option. We want to figure out what’s the minimal footprint. How much do we really need to do and who do we need to do it in to really catch [COVID-19]? We’ve been using a computational modeling approach. We’re gathering information about how people move in the school. Then, from there, we can run simulations with this computational model and figure out where the likeliest places for transmission to occur and then concentrate testing at those hubs.

“I’m very happy about what we’ve been able to achieve so far, but I still think there’s a huge, heavy lift ahead of us.”

John Foxe, PhD

Kilian J. and Caroline F. Schmitt Chair in Neuroscience, Research Director of The Ernest J. Del Monte Institute for Neuroscience, University of Rochester Medical Center, Rochester, NY

COVID-19 Testing Infrastructures: State of the Science from the Literature

POLICIES TO SUPPORT ROUTINE & SURGE COVID-19 TESTING

Testing for SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19, remains an important strategy for reducing the spread of COVID-19 in communities, even as vaccination rates rise. High-risk or congregate settings—such as, but not limited to, correctional and detention facilities, long-term care facilities (LTCs), healthcare environments, colleges and universities, schools, and faith-based organizations—must take care in developing testing strategies that can handle volume, identify cases quickly, and are able to be scaled according to changes in case rates.

In correctional facilities, shared bathrooms, cramped quarters, and regular traffic of visitors and staff make transmission more likely.¹ A testing protocol and regular screening program can help identify pre- and asymptomatic cases before the virus spreads. Asymptomatic spread is when someone without symptoms unknowingly spreads the virus.² Testing and screening is also critical in LTC settings, such as nursing homes, which have a high proportion of high-risk residents.³ While LTC facilities are widely using rapid antigen tests for screening, there have been concerns about their accuracy, with some states even blocking their use due to high rates of false positives.⁴ Despite these concerns, rapid antigen testing, when employed according to Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS) guidance, is an important tool in preventing outbreaks. In healthcare environments such as hospitals, workers may be exposed to COVID-19 cases on a regular basis. Some may then unknowingly spread the virus to others if they remain asymptomatic, or in the days before their symptoms develop. Weekly screening of workers may help reduce transmission.⁵ Organizations that provide services to unhoused people also need to take great care to keep the communities they serve safe. In addition to regularly testing employees, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recommends such organizations work with local health departments, housing authorities, and local community organizations and businesses to ensure resources are available for people who have symptoms of

COVID-19 and need to be tested or have tested positive and need to quarantine.⁶

In colleges and universities, modifications may need to be made to the number of students living on campus, as well as to testing strategies. During the fall 2020 semester, Duke University decreased the number of students living on campus;⁷ they also set up pooled surveillance testing and contact tracing for all students and staff. Pooled testing for COVID-19 means taking samples from many students, combining those samples into one large batch, and PCR testing the entire batch. If a batch test comes back positive, it does not identify which student in the batch had the positive result. Therefore, the samples are then tested individually to find the one (or more) individuals with a positive test result. This reduces the total number of tests that need to be performed, particularly when the frequency of positive samples is low. The university then initiates contact tracing for individual positive cases. Pooled testing offers a cost-effective way to go beyond symptomatic-only testing. Duke University also observed that 51 percent of positive COVID-19 tests came from people who were

You need to make testing as **easy** as possible, remove as many of the barriers as you can, be **flexible**, be **mobile**.

John Foxe, PhD

asymptomatic. This indicates that only testing symptomatic people may be inadequate.⁸⁻¹⁰ Organizations and communities also need to be able to be flexible with rapidly changing guidance and technology. The National Football League (NFL) had established a definition of “high-risk” contact over 15 minutes of interaction between two people; however, when they found that transmission occurred in instances with less duration of contact, they revised their definition, mask protocol, and ventilation strategy.¹¹

Regardless of what combination of testing, screening, or surveillance strategies an organization employs, contact tracing is a critical part of managing the virus. A successful contact tracing program can be difficult to implement. Specifically, catching and managing cases before they surface is difficult, especially with asymptomatic spread.^{10,12} Contact tracing also needs to account for the communities most impacted, as social and economic insecurity makes it more difficult to participate in testing and contact tracing programs.^{13,14} If contact tracing programs only reach

communities that are well off, then they can actually worsen health disparities. While digital solutions such as contact tracing apps hold promise,¹⁵ they may leave out those who do not own smartphones,¹⁶ as well as those who may have data privacy concerns.¹⁷ One review of COVID-19 contact tracing apps available in the United States also found that 69 percent exceeded a ninth-grade reading level, 65 percent were available only in English, and only 12 percent included inclusive illustrations, limiting their accessibility to certain communities and populations.¹⁸ Social workers and community health workers may prove valuable assets in contact tracing efforts in communities. Social workers could not only help identify other possible infections, but also help address community needs and link people to services.¹⁹ In many low- and middle-income nations, community health workers have played critical roles in contact tracing and raising community awareness during pandemics.²⁰

Ensuring accessibility is essential to reaching the communities most impacted by the pandemic. Mobile clinics

offer one way to address disparities in access, offering a mechanism to connect with hardly reached communities. In Baltimore, Maryland, LifeBridge Health piloted a mobile health clinic that provided PCR tests for communities high on the Vulnerability Index. This service met a critical need in the predominantly Black/African American population served.^{21,22} UNC Health, which is based in Chapel Hill, North Carolina, partnered with community leaders to turn a vascular screening unit into a mobile testing site to serve Black and Latinx communities in the surrounding area. They covered the cost of testing for uninsured patients through grant and foundation support. They worked with a community advisory board to determine the best locations for testing sites, engage local community organizations, and advertise the testing sites. The community advisory board also flagged barriers to a trusting relationship, including a perceived lack of long-term commitment on the part of UNC Health, and fears that community suggestions might not be truly incorporated.²³ These types of off-site testing centers provide great value to communities by expanding services to needs beyond COVID-19, such as nutritional support, HIV screening, Medicaid enrollment counseling, and referrals to other health providers. Off-site testing centers should partner with local community and faith-based²⁴ organizations, prioritize patient experiences, and ensure timely patient results. Healthcare systems should build or further leverage mobile clinics as a part of expanded healthcare infrastructure and emergency preparedness. Additional research is also needed on both the economic and social impacts of off-site testing centers and mobile clinics to support their adoption.²⁵

Providing multiple ways to get a test may also help ensure equitable access. The University of Illinois Hospital set up a drive-through and walk-up testing center in Chicago, focused on reaching racial and ethnic minorities. Half of the participants were Black or Latinx residents. Black residents were more likely to use the walk-up option, indicating the importance of different options for testing delivery.²⁶ In April 2020, the state of Michigan set up a task force to address racial disparities in COVID-19 outcomes. As a part of their work to address these disparities, they administered 24,000 free tests and established multiple ways of getting a test in underserved areas, including mobile testing, drive-through testing, and walk-up testing in 21 neighborhoods primarily in Detroit. They also provided wraparound services

to quarantined individuals, such as food and housing assistance.²⁷ Providing options for affordable (or free) self-testing kits is one way to scale up testing in communities. However, those from higher-income communities or backgrounds may be more willing to self-test for COVID-19,²⁸ indicating the need for targeted awareness campaigns in marginalized, highly impacted communities. [Say Yes! COVID Test](#)—a partnership between the CDC and the NIH to bring free COVID-19 testing to communities—works with local

What do parents need to know to really give informed consent for a test or for a vaccine?

How do I get the right interpreter for this family, maybe somebody that they trust, so that they believe this information that we're sharing with them is valid?

Karen Zandi

public health departments in five cities (as of September 2021) to offer free at-home COVID-19 testing to all residents. Such an initiative could help increase access and awareness in the communities that need them most.²⁹

[IN CONTEXT] Community Perspective: Karen Zandi

RADx-UP Project: COV-IDD: Testing for COVID-19 in High-Risk Children With Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities, University of Rochester, New York

“I want to insert, both for testing and for vaccinations as we get into that, the important thing is our relationship with our parents and our families, because we know what they are battling at the forefront. [What do parents] need to know to

really give informed consent for a test or for a vaccine? How do I get the right interpreter for this family, maybe somebody that they trust, so that they believe this information that we’re sharing with them is valid? [...]

“[Many of the kids’] parents speak a language other than English. When the kids are in school, they’re learning English and having a [physical therapy] session. ‘We’re going to move your right arm now.’ A mom who speaks another language can’t understand what the [physical therapist] wants her to do when you’re remote.

“We had huge expense and challenges in figuring out interpreters and how we support families. Even [the logistics] of who has internet. We delivered [internet] hotspots to families. We delivered iPads out to the community, because a family with four kids and [they’ve only got] his

mom’s phone to Zoom on—that’s not going to work.

“We put a lot of resources immediately into the hands of our families, beyond groceries and diapers. If somebody’s COVID positive and a parent can’t go to the store because [they’re] now in quarantine, how do I get groceries? They don’t have credit cards. [They] can’t do the GrubHub or food delivery [services.] We were really about food, clothing, and shelter and basic interventions early on.

“Philosophically, you understand who we are. Our teams here are about, ‘Let’s get it done.’ I can’t say enough about how much our direct care staff, our clinical staff, and our leadership just all jumped in. We’re pretty tired, but we’re ready for the next round. So, that’s us.”

Karen Zandi
President & CEO of the Mary Cariola Center, Rochester, New York

COVID-19 TESTING IN SCHOOLS

In the spring of 2020, schools across the United States closed because of the uncertainty about the role they might have in community spread of COVID-19. Researchers have since gained greater understanding about the harms of limiting in-person education and how to keep schools safely open. In 2020, school closures affected more than 55.1 million children in the United States and many of these children experienced negative effects including increased rates of depression, anxiety, suicidality, and absenteeism, coupled with concerns about equal access to quality education.³⁰ Children in Black, Indigenous, and people of color (BIPOC) communities and children with intellectual and developmental disabilities were more likely to experience both the negative impacts of missing school and the health impacts of COVID-19.³¹

As the 2021-2022 school year brings in-person learning back to nearly all communities in the United States, researchers have many lessons to share on how to keep schools safe:

- As part of its COVID-19 mitigation strategy, New York City public schools implemented random testing of asymptomatic people at least once per month and

increased to once per week as the rate of COVID-19 in the community increased. At the time of their study published in *Pediatrics* in May 2021, COVID-19 prevalence in New York City schools was no higher than in the larger community. Of all positive COVID-19 cases in the community, only 0.5 percent were contracted in the school. An estimated 78 percent of the cases contracted within the school were staff-to-staff or staff-to-student transmissions.³²

- Students in a New Jersey school signed a “Best for All” contract with the school that asked them to adhere to specific guidelines in their personal time away from school. These guidelines included adhering to social distancing, masking, and hygiene practices. Students wore a personal tracer device while on campus (except while in their rooms, the shower, or the pool) to assist with contact tracing and adherence to the “Best for All” contract. Athletic teams practiced regularly but did not participate in interscholastic events. Extracurricular activities were held in the school with full social distancing, masking, and hygiene practices. With all of these measures in place, only two cases of COVID-19 were contracted in the school.³³

- Schools in Utah and New Jersey adopted routine testing programs for children participating in extracurricular activities. Testing allowed schools to determine if COVID-19 was being spread during these activities and allowed students to remain in school five days a week with a negative test.³⁴
- Researchers have found that diagnostic testing of individuals exposed to COVID-19 was as effective as quarantine in preventing in-school transmission and that weekly universal screening prevents 50 percent of the transmission of COVID-19 in a school. Surveillance testing is useful in finding larger outbreak clusters while requiring fewer resources than screening testing. In

the “test-to-stay” strategy, students with symptoms of COVID-19 remained in school and took rapid tests each day they had symptoms, isolating only after a positive test. Likewise, students exposed to COVID-19 also remained in school, taking rapid daily tests for a week, isolating only after a positive test. The “test-to-stay” program shows great potential for increasing in-person school days while keeping the expenditure of testing low. Although a screening test mitigation strategy has the highest testing costs, it can reduce the societal costs associated with lost days of in-person school and potential COVID-19 transmission in the school.³⁰

[IN CONTEXT] Community Perspective: Tinka Duran, MPH

RADx-UP project: Understanding Testing Decisions in Great Plains American Indians, Massachusetts General Hospital, South Dakota

“Historically, we’ve faced hurdles in accessing tribal data with federal, state, and local governments. [That’s because of] low numbers and identifications, but then also misclassification. Indian Health Services and others have done

studies regarding misclassification and death rates to address disease burden and health disparities. Accessing American Indian/ Alaska Native (AI/AN) data can be challenging.

“Each tribe is different, so their data sharing agreements may be different [from one] tribe to another. It’s important to understand that throughout the tribes. [That means] coming to the table and working with the tribe and understanding what they will and won’t share with you and making sure that you’re going through that approval process. Before you start any type of research, you need to know about the time that it takes to get that approval process as well. [...]”

“I advocate for our tribes to make sure that research and policy

development is done hand-in-hand with the tribe. That we continue to do community Based Participatory Research (CBPR) [and that the] tribes are at the table.... That the tribe has buy-in, they have persons working on the project, not just giving guidance. It’s that whole piece of CBPR...

“I want to make sure that our tribes are able to use the data. [The data] does not belong to us. [It] belongs to the tribe. They can tell us what they will let us use [it for], how to use it, what you can and cannot do with it. That data is not ours, it’s the tribes and that’s very, very important. Working in partnership with the tribes can lead to sustainable and long-term successful partnerships in decreasing health disparities in our tribal communities.”

Tinka Duran, MPH

Director of Prevention Programs for the Great Plains Tribal Leaders Health Board, Rapid City, South Dakota

DATA SHARING EQUITY

The COVID-19 pandemic has renewed the importance of sharing health data so researchers can more quickly ask and answer clinical research and public health planning and response questions. In the wake of the outbreak, all manner of COVID-19 data—the viral genome, incubation periods, method of transmission, etc.—were exchanged as soon as possible. Data sharing allows for consistent collection, reporting, and availability of COVID-19 data such as morbidity and mortality, testing and vaccination rates, as well as the size, spread, and distribution of the disease.³⁵ There is a need for more efficient and consistent data sharing between hospitals and public health officials and state and federal governments.³⁶ The general public and decision makers (especially those representing vulnerable communities) also need better access to comprehensible data and more transparency when it comes to the source of the data and its limitations.^{36–39}

Access to data is important because it allows for identification of health disparities and inequities (especially among vulnerable populations), allocation and distribution patterns of vaccinations, testing, therapeutics, other health services, and additional patterns that may otherwise go unnoticed.^{40,41}

Availability of this knowledge holds decision makers accountable and informs COVID-19 mitigation efforts, monitoring, and surveillance.^{38,42} National and state policy that impact the communities most affected by COVID-19 can be tailored based on the information that comes to light. For example, allocation of resources related to testing, vaccinations, and healthcare may need to be adjusted to account for health disparities among vulnerable populations.^{42–44} Vulnerable populations in this context may feel the effects of COVID-19 disproportionately, lack political power, and lack data sovereignty. Indigenous populations, for example, are more likely to experience severe outcomes of COVID-19 but lack access to timely and accurate health data important for resource allocation to their communities.⁴²

Data may also inform nonpolicy approaches to healthcare delivery and overall population health, the ability of public health agencies to monitor and quickly react to outbreaks, and future research and planning.^{38,45,46} If vulnerable communities have access to data about themselves, they can make informed decisions and assert greater sovereignty.³⁸

A lack of accurate, complete, and consistent data can lead to misinformation and distrust, especially among historically marginalized communities; underestimates of severity; less

efficient research; erasure of groups not represented in data, leading to continued harms; and a lack of understanding as to whether the interventions we leverage against COVID-19 are effective—or whether we are responding at all.^{36–38,48}

The importance of data to a proper COVID-19 response underscores the need to build and sustain public health data infrastructure to support a rapid national response at all levels and curb the toll of the pandemic.^{39,42,45} Proponents argue the severity of COVID-19 merits an appropriate response—though it will take an extraordinary effort.^{35,45}

The tribe can tell us what they will let us use the data for, how to use it, what you can and cannot do with it. That data is not ours—it's the tribes—and that's very, very important.

Tinka Duran, MPH

Despite this significance, there is currently a lack of data sharing. It is often difficult to coordinate data sharing and ensure data quality. Challenges include a lack of resources and capacity among staff dealing with data; information gaps between hospitals and health agencies; insufficient consistency between state and federal testing data; a lack of uniform data sharing agreements or data standards between institutions; and a failure on the part of the federal government to share data with Indigenous decision makers and scientists.^{37,38,45–47}

Implementing data sharing is costly, and many organizations lack the resources, know-how, or infrastructure to meet

the demand for data.^{37,45} One study found that 41 percent of hospitals seeking to report surveillance data to local, state, and federal public health agencies were prevented from doing so because public health agencies lacked the capacity to electronically receive the data, while 32 percent of hospitals cited the cost and complexity of the interface.⁴⁶ The disparities between published state and federal testing data have been attributed to the low quality of data submitted to the federal government and a strain on resources at the state level.³⁶ Sometimes it is unclear where the data are coming from. Even for those with the means, data sharing requires time and effort and the platforms that facilitate sharing while simultaneously respecting privacy.³⁷ Inconsistent reporting of data and a lack of data standards also make it difficult to track and compare. To further complicate collecting and comparing state-level COVID-19 testing data, data are defined and presented differently between states. Reporting of mortality data is particularly unreliable because some states are less transparent about backlogs in processing, and death certificates can be misclassified or missing altogether.³⁸

Race and ethnicity data are further limited by underreporting and misclassification.³⁷ Though there are regulations in place to encourage reporting on race and ethnicity for COVID-19 cases in the United States since June 2020, compliance is inadequate. Over half of health departments did not report all racial and ethnic groups consistent with Office of Management and Budget guidelines in 2020, though reporting of racial and ethnic data increases after the Equitable Data Collection and Disclosure on COVID-19 Act was introduced in Congress.³⁷ There has also been a failure to disaggregate data on Indigenous communities by region of residence, as well as inaccurate reporting of race and ethnicity data at both the individual and group level. This includes the use of the “other” category or the inability to select more than one race or ethnicity category.⁴⁷ Lack of proper representation in data can lead to systemic erasure of already vulnerable populations, such as American Indian and Alaska Native communities, as well as make it difficult to assess and mitigate the impact of COVID-19.⁴⁷

Other vulnerable populations suffer from a lack of representation in data, as well. Only 69 percent of jurisdictions reported COVID-19 data on correctional facilities in the spring of 2020.¹ These data are important

because prisons, in particular, have struggled to contain COVID-19.

Overall, there are not enough data points being collected, and the lack of nuance can impact policy.³⁷ A lack of data sharing and poor data quality make it more difficult to target and evaluate public health and clinical interventions.⁴⁸ But there are ethical, legal, and political boundaries to consider when it comes to data collection.³⁷ For example, Indigenous communities often lack access to and control over their own data, which leads to dependency on those who do collect it and limited decision-making capacity.^{38,42} One study found that case data on tribal lands, published on New Mexico's state dashboard without tribal permission, led to a hospital policy that singled out Native American patients and required them to undergo COVID-19 testing. There were no explicit options for refusing or requesting the testing, and pregnant Indigenous women affected by the policy were sometimes separated from their newborns while awaiting test results.³⁸

In the long term, academia is not structured to encourage scientists to share data. One analysis concluded that the sharing of information during the pandemic was conditional at best.³⁹ After the pandemic is over, a lack of incentives to share hard-won data in a competitive environment will continue to be the biggest limitation to data sharing between academic researchers.³⁹

There is a need to design simpler, more efficient, and more timely infrastructure for data sharing. Improving data sharing technology by identifying technology gaps, repurposing existing technology like electronic health records to facilitate data sharing in the short term, publishing open data in machine-actionable formats, and prioritizing investment in health system IT infrastructure could help alleviate some of the most cited technological barriers to data sharing identified above.^{37,45,46}

Health data are accumulating constantly in hospital systems and need to be shared between parties to facilitate large-scale, real-time analysis for a quicker response to the next public health emergency.³⁵ Data consolidation between

Cultural competence is always important, but it becomes particularly dire when we are dealing with the type of public health threat that we're facing right now.

Ilana Dubester

entities can make data analytics easier and more consistent. By combining data from healthcare provider organizations, public health departments, and other settings that generate health data, public health entities can apply computable knowledge to combat the pandemic in a broader learning health ecosystem.^{35,45}

Other ways to reduce the burden on health officials include identifying available data and collaborating with other officials to determine a minimum data set; increasing the availability of technical assistance to states from the federal government; and improving funding for vulnerable communities so they can have their own data infrastructure and independently decrease negative COVID-19 outcomes.^{36,38,45}

Documentation and reporting of data have to become more consistent if comparing data is going to be fruitful. It needs to be made clear where data is coming from; states should provide clear documentation of COVID-19 electronic laboratory reporting data sources.³⁶ There is also a need for standardized reporting of demographic data across the United States, especially data disaggregated by race and ethnicity data (including Indigenous communities), so that resources can be allocated according to need.^{37,38} Passing the Equitable Data Collection and Disclosure on COVID-19 Act has been identified as a good first step.⁴⁴ Infrastructure for monitoring data quality can help identify other areas where documentation and reporting need to be improved.³⁷

Data sharing agreements should be created to facilitate the exchange of standardized information between

relevant organizations. Sharing data and resources between healthcare systems, public health agencies, and community-based organizations can improve quality of care and save lives, but infrastructure is needed to enable sharing.⁴⁴ Sharing data with the public can help them track and mitigate the spread of the disease, but appropriate messengers for data sharing will need to be identified.³⁷ Policy makers should set reporting requirements for local public health agencies so it is clear what data should be made publicly available and how it should be reported.³⁷ States should also work with journalists and public health researchers to communicate the context and limitations of the data.⁴⁹

Vulnerable communities, especially, should be party to data that implicate them and empower them to make informed decisions for their communities. For example, a preexisting data sharing agreement between the government of Canada and First Nations' communities allowed them to collaborate on a quick response to the disease.³⁸

Similarly, relevant organizations should be involved in the design of data sharing infrastructure. Public health departments can address some of their technological limitations by codesigning a process for data sharing so they can identify shared data elements and actionable data transfer formats.⁴⁵ Indigenous leaders, activists, scholars, and members of the public can contribute Indigenous knowledge to guide data practices in their communities and should be included in mainstream decision making.³⁸

Space needs to be made to engage in critical discussion with others both in the field and from other sectors about the role of data, its implications, and potential consequences of data sharing.^{45,47} Multi-institutional coordinating activities for organizations with complementary needs, expertise, and capabilities can be used to facilitate discussion and share resources, best practices, and, of course, data.

After the pandemic ends, there will still be significant value in open information sharing. More efficient infrastructure will need to be created to facilitate the exchange of data for the improvement of health outcomes at home and abroad.³⁹

[IN CONTEXT] Community Perspective: Ilana Dubester

RADx-UP Project: Adapting Community-Based Task-Shifting for the COVID-19 Response Among Underserved Populations in Piedmont, North Carolina (ACT-UP), University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, North Carolina

The Hispanic Liaison is an advocacy, organizing, leadership development, and direct services organization based in Siler City and Sanford. It serves the Latino community in Chatham, Alamance, Randolph, and Lee counties.

“Cultural competence is critical for this infrastructure, because one size doesn’t fit all. We need to think about all the different angles and the different people that need access to

information, the different levels of education, different levels of trust in the system, and different levels of access to documentation and health insurance. We need to think about the entire population we’re trying to reach, not just cater to the lowest common denominator.

“Cultural competence of all cultures is a fundamental piece in public health... especially when we’re dealing with a situation like a pandemic or any kind of disease outbreak that threatens everyone. Cultural competence is always important, but it becomes particularly dire when we are dealing with the type of public health threat that we’re facing right now.

“Communication is not just about translating materials that were created in English, but creating materials in Spanish that resonate with the target community. The information being produced was too scientific, too slick, and too wordy for community members who don’t have as much formal education.

Our approach for folks with less formal education is to keep sentences short, using the simplest ways to explain

things, and adding visuals as well for those who can’t read; many in our community can’t read well. It’s about understanding where the community comes from, understanding their concerns, and tailoring information to them.

“They may choose not to put the energy into it, or they may not value it as much because they don’t believe that these community members are just as valuable to the process as those who are translating the information to make it more accessible for all. If we’re talking about health equity, it means everyone has equal opportunity to the information; everyone should be treated and valued the same.

“I think that’s hard because how do you convince somebody of that? There has to be a willingness to understand that not everyone has a university degree and can read those papers, and a real awareness that unless we’re inclusive of everyone, we are all in trouble.”

Ilana Dubester
Founder & Executive Director of El Vinculo Hispano, Siler City, North Carolina

ESTABLISHING COMMUNICATIONS FRAMEWORKS

From social distancing guidelines to best testing practices to vaccine information, information about COVID-19 has been in flux over the past year. Facilitating the exchange of information can improve COVID-19 outcomes and leave us better prepared for the next public health crisis. Bidirectional communication between community members, government officials, and academics can help guide research and policy. Members of the public can provide insight into uptake of COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and other mitigation strategies in their communities, which can then help guide future interventions and potentially improve outcomes. In a study examining COVID-19 perceptions among African Americans in under-resourced communities in Alabama, participants identified barriers and facilitators to uptake of preventative measures and testing.⁵² Researchers were then able to identify what future interventions would need to provide in order to increase community acceptance among Black Alabamians, a population with pronounced health disparities.

More clear, consistent, and tailored communication from government and health officials can help establish trust within communities and mitigate risk by increasing adherence to public health measures.^{52,53} For example, South Korea's success at containing the virus has been attributed in part to the confidence built through the government's transparent and frequent communication with the public.⁵⁴ Information can also empower citizens to participate in disease prevention and containment as well as decision making tailored to their communities' needs.⁵⁵ Communication between government officials at the national, regional, and local levels is also essential for

planning a coordinated response and sharing resources, information, and best practices.⁵⁴

There are population-specific concerns that can impact the reach of information about COVID-19. In one study, researchers spoke to Latinx individuals who had been hospitalized for COVID-19. Some patients cited economic and immigration fears as driving both exposure and delay in seeking care.⁵³ They concluded that teaching safe practices and providing explicit health messaging about the relationship between health care and immigration enforcement were among the communication strategies needed. Other population-specific considerations, like language, cultural differences, and accessibility for people with disabilities must be accounted for when planning communication.^{52,55,56}

Researchers may lack the linguistic and cultural competency needed for their work to be accepted or seen as credible and culturally appropriate.^{23,57} Objectification, lack of commitment, a history of racist treatment and abuse of BIPOC communities, and a failure to include them in research and planning have rendered researchers and academic institutions untrustworthy to racial and ethnic minority communities.^{23,57-59} This distrust extends to healthcare systems and government, as well, and can impact community receptiveness to information about COVID-19 testing and vaccination coming from these sources.^{59,61,62}

Nor is this an issue unique to reaching vulnerable populations. One study found that political partisanship was a significant driver of vaccine hesitancy among White survey respondents, and distrust of the government and/or COVID-19 vaccines was reported by 31 percent of White respondents.⁶³ Distrust of the government was also cited

Disagreement doesn't mean disrespect or dismissal, but what it needs to do is allow us to **hear each other's voices.**

Mary Ricketts

as a major reason for vaccine hesitancy among staff in skilled nursing facilities, along with doubts about the vaccine development process and concerns about preexisting medical conditions.⁶⁴ Misinformation contributes to distrust of health authorities and government officials as well, and there has been plenty of it; the majority of news consumers and 48 percent of people in the United States have been exposed to misinformation about COVID-19.⁶⁵

A lack of clear and consistent communication can feed into misunderstanding and the spread of misinformation.⁵² Frequently changing messaging from public health officials and the media about vaccination eligibility, supply, and efficacy against new strains was identified as a contributing factor in vaccine hesitancy in minority populations.⁶¹ Inadequate information and mixed messages from government officials and medical practitioners has been cited as a driver of misunderstanding about the importance of following COVID-19 guidelines in young Black populations.⁵²

Logistically speaking, the need for social distancing during COVID-19 has moved communication between communities and decision makers online. Barriers to virtual alternatives such as a lack of internet access or technical knowledge can preclude certain groups from accessing information or sharing their input.⁵⁵ Older populations were identified as having the least knowledge about connecting to and effectively using the internet.⁵² Therefore, the shift to virtual communication—though necessary to sustain partnerships with communities over the course of the pandemic—has alienated some of the groups most impacted by COVID-19.

Given these considerations, there are several ways to improve communication between policy makers, healthcare professionals, public health officials, academia, and the communities they serve during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In bidirectional information exchange between community members and academic researchers, community members can contribute intimate knowledge of their spaces, such as historical context and insight into local needs and assets and help to make more informed decisions.⁶⁶ In turn, researchers can share the resources they have access to through their institutions, such as the latest relevant information and technology assistance and training. This strategy can improve COVID-19 outcomes by informing policy and research approaches, as well as empowering communities

by giving them the tools to implement and disseminate new knowledge and participate in decision making.⁶⁶

It can also help rebuild trust, especially in vulnerable communities.⁶⁰ In a study reviewing promising practices for off-site COVID-19 testing centers, community leaders indicated that trust could be gained by developing community partnerships, listening to community members, and becoming educated on the issues impacting them.²² Town hall meetings, for example, could be a forum where researchers and community members come together to meet, ask questions, and share information.⁵⁷

Infrastructure from existing academic-community partnerships can be leveraged to facilitate bidirectional information exchange related to COVID-19.⁶⁷ However, they must be sustained so that partners can build on existing trust and mutual respect in the event of the next public health crisis and beyond.⁶⁸ If no community partnerships exist, establishing them now will also help prepare for future collaborations.⁶⁹

Collaboration with community members can also lead to more culturally tailored approaches. Health risk messaging, for example, can be written to be culturally and linguistically appropriate and relevant to the community it is addressing.⁶⁰ In one successful information campaign, a collaborative children's book about overcoming COVID-19 was rewritten for Indigenous children and families to reflect their values, experiences, and strengths.⁷⁰ The positive response to the project indicates the demand for targeted communication.

Trusted messengers are also a valuable resource for communicating information, especially in vulnerable communities. These can include community members, spiritual leaders, community-based organizations, local health departments, and trusted health professionals (especially those who are part of the community they serve).^{40,53,65,71} Social media and more traditional channels, like public service announcements and phone calls, can also be go-to sources for information, depending on the community.^{65,67} Some successful efforts have nominated community-based communication leaders, who leverage their own social networks to share information.⁵⁵ Finally,

local coordination points like churches and health centers can be good places to initiate community engagement.⁶⁰

Some existing frameworks can be integrated into these communication strategies. The Mayo Clinic's FAITH program, which focuses on COVID-19 risk communication and emergency preparedness, used the CDC Crisis and Emergency Risk Communication (CDC-CERC) framework.⁶⁷ They deployed it within their existing community-based participatory research partnership with African American churches.

Regular, clear communication can help combat misunderstanding, misinformation, and distrust. Clearly communicating procedures for testing and licensing a COVID-19 vaccine can help alleviate misgivings about its development, for example.⁶¹ On the topic of testing, one successful off-site testing center noted that communication about the specifics of testing, what it means, and what it is in both scientific and lay terms could reduce public anxiety.²² Transparency, consistency, adaptiveness, realism, reflectiveness, and willingness to address historical

[IN CONTEXT] Community Perspective: Mary Ricketts

RADx-UP Project: Improving the Response of Local Urban and Rural Communities to Disparities in COVID-19 Testing, University of Kansas Medical Center, Kansas

“When we think about building infrastructure, I need to know that

Mary Ricketts

Director of Operations of the NBC Community Development Corporation, Kansas City, Kansas

I can trust you and your area of expertise. I also need to know that you're listening to me when it comes to what my specific needs are. If I've hired you to build my house, you'll know the details of laying a solid foundation, but I still have the right to select what color I want my walls painted.

“What you can tell me is where your area of expertise is that mine is not. You can tell me how thick the foundation needs to be based on what's needed in my state and my county and my community. And some of that we are not going to know or understand if we don't have open dialogue.

“Disagreement doesn't mean disrespect or dismissal, but what it needs to do is allow us to hear each other's voices. I need to hear what's coming from research. I need to hear what's coming from community in order to assist those who are making policies. We have to hear each other with an open mindset and appreciate and respect the different perspectives. So, when infrastructure is being built, I have to know that I can trust you, that you have my best interest at heart. And guess what? On the other side, I need to know that when I come to you with facts and data, that you will at least listen.”

[IN CONTEXT] Community Perspective: Broderick Crawford

RADx-UP Project: Improving the Response of Local Urban and Rural Communities to Disparities in COVID-19 Testing, University of Kansas Medical Center, Kansas

“[When thinking of building infrastructure], I think we use construction as our foundation metaphor. [In] Kansas and Missouri,

Broderick Crawford
President of the NBC Community Development Corporation, Kansas City, Kansas

having worked for a contractor, curbs and gutters are different in each state. You might need six-inch curbs and gutters in Missouri but twelve-inch in Kansas. You're still using the same trucks, you're using the same rocks, you're using the same rebar, but you have to use it differently. Well, it's the same thing when we approached COVID in our communities.

“Wyandotte County [in Kansas] is one of the most heavily hit counties... But when you look at the Northeast portion of Wyandotte County or the Western portion of Wyandotte County or the northern portion of Wyandotte County or the southern portion of Wyandotte County, those

are four different communities. Those are four distinctly different communities. Even within the county we've got to be able to adjust.

“What works up in Quindaro is not going to work in Rosedale. What works west of 635 is not going to work on 7th and Minnesota.

“How do we adjust the tools that we have to make it work in each of these communities? It is so important then to get community input. If we don't have community input, then often what we have is top-down approaches. We have those with all the letters behind their name dictating or telling people, ‘We know what's best for you.’ No decisions about us without us...”

injustices have also been identified in the literature as priorities for clear communication with the public.⁶¹

Health officials can improve the clarity of their messaging and develop effective guidelines and principles by coordinating at the national, regional, and local levels.⁵⁴ Local health departments can build their emergency and risk communication capacity on the ground by developing a coordinated approach among staff members and keeping a trained communications professional on staff.⁵⁵

By establishing efficient communication frameworks and building relationships now, we can strengthen our ability to respond to future crises. In the long term, those involved with communication during COVID-19 need to emphasize the importance of long-term investment in infrastructure that allows for healthy and productive communities, including public health, primary health care, and community partners.⁶⁰

PANDEMIC PREPAREDNESS

Many of the lessons researchers have learned from the COVID-19 pandemic can be applied to future health emergencies, including ideas about testing, workforce capacity, and telemedicine. We have learned that implementing a testing strategy that can scale from individuals to communities poses challenges for those undertaking it at the organizational, state, and national levels.¹² Federal, state, and local governments need interlocking strategies of testing, contact tracing, and supported isolation. “Readiness frameworks” are needed to guide testing implementation strategies and support local health leaders, tribal nations, and public health officials to establish testing and isolation resources.⁷² A federally supported board could help secure testing supply and infrastructure, set goals for testing, and ensure coordination with supply chain and contact tracing sectors. Such a coordinated federal strategy could help local health authorities navigate the pandemic.⁷² State and local governments may also benefit from risk assessment tools to identify communities that should be prioritized.⁷³ They could then collaborate with communities to facilitate testing, identify short-term and long-term testing needs (e.g., type of test needed, funding and supply, data reporting), find

equitably located testing sites, and reduce barriers to testing.⁷⁴

To help understand and track changing variants, the United States may also benefit from a national genomic surveillance program for SARS-CoV-2 to better track patterns in COVID-19 transmission.⁷⁵ (Please see [reference guide on COVID-19 testing](#) for more information about the types and applications of COVID-19 tests.) Genomic epidemiology involves sequencing the genetic material of samples of the SARS-CoV-2 virus to better understand the source and nature of an outbreak and to monitor communities for new variants of the virus that might have higher transmissibility. Genomic sequencing allowed researchers to find variants that developed in South Africa, Brazil, and India. While useful, genomic epidemiology has many factors that can impact its utility, such as inconsistency in genomic analysis and variations in testing volume and approach.¹² A national disease surveillance program could help monitor communities for outbreaks or hotspots and help inform policies for social distancing and travel restrictions.⁷²

The pandemic has also revealed the need for equitable access to COVID-19 testing and vaccinations. In some areas, resources for testing are allocated disproportionately to

more affluent communities and neighborhoods than those with greater need.⁷⁶ Access to testing and vaccinations may be more difficult for Latinx immigrants and noncitizen immigrants,⁷⁷ LGBTQ communities,⁷⁸ Black/African American communities, American Indian and Alaska Native communities,^{79–81} and people living in rural and under-resourced areas.^{82,83} In addition to the stressors of the COVID-19 pandemic, these communities face ongoing social and structural determinants of health. They may live in larger households, lack regular transportation, have greater difficulty accessing healthcare resources, face language barriers and discrimination, and struggle with unemployment or underemployment. In addition to leading to poorer health outcomes overall, these social determinants of health are correlated with greater risk of getting COVID-19.^{51,82,84}

Mobile clinics, booth clinics, and home testing are additional approaches that might be more successful in these communities.⁸¹ Pharmacy-based COVID-19 testing could meet the testing needs of many communities, and federal or state coordination could help develop a strategy for

identifying pharmacies that need to have testing to meet the needs of a given area or region.⁸⁵ However, “pharmacy deserts,” areas where there are few or no pharmacies, lead to disparities in access to vaccinations and testing. One analysis of geographic accessibility of pharmacies found that there were more pharmacy deserts in Black and Latinx neighborhoods than in White neighborhoods, regardless of whether the neighborhoods were medically underserved areas.⁸⁶ To help avoid pharmacy deserts, Medicare and Medicaid could offer higher reimbursement rates for pharmacies at risk of closing.⁸⁶

Pandemic response plans include plans for healthcare systems increasing, or surging, workforce capacity in the case of increased COVID-19 cases. Early in the pandemic, shortages and uneven distribution of certain health professionals such as acute care nurses and respiratory therapists sparked concerns. Healthcare systems, in partnership with state and local health departments, can surge the workforce by calling upon retired or inactive health workers, upskilling health professionals to take on needed roles, and fast-tracking medical students.⁸⁷ The Harvard

Roadmap to Pandemic Resilience recommends expanding the US Public Health Service corps and Medical Reserve Corps into a Health Reserve Corps. Such an organization could help fill gaps in staffing around the nation, redeploying existing nurses and physician assistants to quickly surge the number of health workers available in the communities that need them.⁷² This Health Reserves Corps could also leverage a community health workforce that could provide contact tracing support, help communities expand testing and COVID-19 vaccine uptake, and address underlying social needs. Many community health workers may share similar lived experience to the people they work with, making them a trusted source of health information and guidance. In working on the ground with local community organizations, community health workers can also take on a role in risk

How do we adjust the tools that we have to make it work in each of these communities?

Broderick Crawford

assessment and identification. Many low- and middle-income countries have successfully used community health workers for contact tracing during pandemics. Community health workers may also play a role in advocating for COVID-19 vaccination.⁸⁸ In addition to considering the workforce itself, health systems need to ensure equitable access to personal protective equipment for all health workers, including those in auxiliary roles such as administration, cleaning, and transportation. They also need to consider the psychological health and larger well-being of their frontline health workforce, who are at increased risk of burnout.⁸⁷

Another way to ease pressure on the healthcare workforce is a shift to telemedicine. In the past year, infrastructure

to support telemedicine has been an invaluable part of pandemic preparedness for healthcare systems. In the spring of 2020, hospitals and healthcare systems had to quickly shift to telemedicine to slow the spread of COVID-19 and protect healthcare workers and patients. Some health systems were able to quickly leverage technology to provide expanded care in a rapidly changing health landscape. The San Francisco Department of Public Health includes both a safety net healthcare delivery system and a population public health system. They serve a culturally and linguistically diverse population. In the beginning of the pandemic, as cases surged in at-risk communities, the health system leveraged their fairly new IT infrastructure to improve care for patients, expand urgent care, stand up a lower-acuity site, and create new electronic health record workflows to support rapid care. They also quickly expanded telehealth and launched mobile health clinics. In the case of San Francisco, robust IT infrastructure was able to support both vulnerable communities and healthcare transformation.⁸⁹

While telehealth offers a wealth of possibilities,⁹⁰ it also poses access challenges that can lead to health disparities. For those without broadband access, telemedicine services such as video calls may be impossible. Many people living in rural areas lack access to broadband. Lack of high-speed internet access is also more common among those living in tribal nations, and as well as in lower-income areas. In scenarios where people cannot access video connection, visits must be audio-only, which may not be reimbursed at the same rate and may not provide the same degree of personal connection between patient and provider. One cross-sectional study examined outpatient visits at an integrated health system in the Upper Midwest during the summer of 2020 and found that, among patients who had a telemedicine visit, those who were older, lived in rural areas, were Black/African American or Hispanic, or did not have insurance were less likely to have a video visit. Those with greater digital literacy were more likely to have a video visit.⁹¹ To be ready for shifts to virtual care, states may need to have initiatives to assist with patient access to broadband.^{92,93} More research is needed around how health systems and states can increase access across the board and create more community-centered approaches to accessing health care.⁹⁴

[IN CONTEXT] Community-Engaged Researcher Perspective: May Okihiro, MD

RADx-UP Project: Community Driven Approach to Mitigate COVID-19 Pacific Alliance Against COVID-19 (PAAC), University of Hawai'i at Manoa, Hawaii

"[Our project] specifically and actively recruits [team members] who are from the community or we [who] used to live in the community and then moved out but still know the community well. We have definitely found that COVID-19 is such a sensitive topic, whether it's testing, or vaccinations, it is a sensitive personal issue even though the

pandemic affects us all. And having people who are from the community who understand the point of view of community members [has] been an essential component of us being able to advertise effectively, [to] get people to come in for testing, [to] understand the results as we've refined our messages. And to [help them access] other services and other resources, as people [have had to] quarantine or [isolate], or want to just talk about vaccination and next steps. Having people from the community, and then also orienting [them] on our research, how our research is different and [it is] important, [how it] impacts the testing we're doing. All of that we've had to very intentionally have discussions with our community team members, [so that they can] convey that information effectively back to community members. [...]

"I think, who is conveying the message is important. So having

people who look like the other community members, are actually recognized by other community members, is important... Many of us on the team, as well as other providers at our health center, have participated in various town hall meetings, small group meetings, many of them by zoom now, [we have] been much more visible. Not to scold people and tell them that they should [get] tested, take their vaccinations, but more just providing information that may have already been in the news, but [providing it] in the context of our community. So, I often will start with some of the statistics from our community, and then bring all along the state statistics and just reflect on risk benefit in a way that hopefully is less threatening, and that's been well received."

May Okihiro, MD

Department of Pediatric HICORE Director, NPCA Healthcare Task force Chair at John A. Burns School of Medicine - University of Hawaii at Manoa, Honolulu, Hawaii

Who is conveying the message is important. So having people who look like the other community members, are actually recognized by other community members, is important...

May Okihiro, MD

STRENGTHENING MULTI-SECTOR PARTNERSHIPS

Partnerships between public organizations and private businesses are essential to building the infrastructure needed for testing and vaccination efforts in the United States. Partnerships might include academic institutions and communities and community-led organizations (such as those represented by RADx-UP projects) or private businesses and public organizations such as health departments and federal and state institutes. These types of partnerships are critical to creating communication coalitions, improving data and contact tracing infrastructure, and advancing the testing and vaccination technologies and approaches needed to address the COVID-19 pandemic.⁹⁵

Public-private partnerships are a crucial part of pandemic preparedness and response, enabling the quick pace of COVID-19 vaccine production and distribution.⁹⁶ For example, Healthcare Ready—a nonprofit organization dedicated to bridging health care, public health, and emergency management to support health preparedness and response—coordinated information between the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the Department of Health and Human Services, and health sector leaders to determine the best suppliers and get supplies to the areas that needed them most. Likewise, the Washington State Department of Health's Vaccine Action Command and Coordination System

Center matched states with private sector resources.⁹⁶ State governments can also form successful partnerships. In the spring of 2020, several states joined an interstate testing compact that worked in conjunction with the Rockefeller Foundation to coordinate acquiring and delivering rapid antigen tests. This compact helped create testing availability without competition between these states.⁹⁷

Given the scale of need, there is more room for growth in these partnerships. A report from the Rockefeller Foundation called for increased national investment in testing and especially rapid testing, targeted delivery of these tests to the communities that need them, local systems to track infections, and better data tracking.⁹⁵ Employers can also be a valuable partner in vaccine distribution and uptake by providing quality communication, transportation assistance, paid time off, and incentives to get vaccinated. Broadly, healthcare systems can play a role in ensuring equitable rollout of vaccines by focusing on the communities they serve who may be most impacted by the pandemic.⁹⁶

American Indian and Alaska Native communities, particularly those living on Tribal lands, face longstanding social and structural inequities, including poor housing and transportation infrastructure.^{79,80} Native leadership, community members, and community organizations have partnered to combat these inequalities and protect the health of their communities. In the spring of 2020, the

Navajo Nation put in place shelter-in-place and curfew regulations and worked to expand testing available to communities. Navajo Nation leadership also worked to ensure information about COVID-19 was available in Indigenous languages, as many Native American elders only speak these languages. Native Health, a community-based organization, expanded their services to provide food for families in need. Native American Peoples also supported each other directly with donation drives and by delivering supplies to those who needed them.⁴⁷

Especially in the context of the pandemic, where health disparities have been apparent, communities are essential partners in conducting research that meaningfully advances the science of COVID-19.^{52,57,98} While community-engaged research is necessary now more than ever with the racial, ethnic, and social inequities reinforced and exacerbated by COVID-19,⁶⁶ the pandemic has posed new challenges to community-engaged research.⁶⁸ Relationship building is usually done in person and embedded in communities. Shifting this work from in-person to remote settings has posed recruitment and engagement challenges. In addition,

many community organizations have had to serve more people and more needs in their communities, leaving them stretched for resources to devote to research.⁶⁶ Despite these hurdles, there have been promising moments in community-engaged research during the pandemic, with the implementation of new, readily responsive strategies and methods. Researchers at the University of Miami found that some solutions—such as phone-based surveys rather than face-to-face surveys—led to increased retention rates for the low-income immigrant community they worked with. Researchers at the University of Kentucky and the Michigan Institute for Clinical and Health Research were able to pivot their focus to directly support the health and social needs of communities. Both institutions worked to ensure communities had accessible communication materials in their native languages.⁶⁶

The pandemic reinforces the need to include community partners and community voices in study design and recruitment⁶⁶, as well as in disseminating results.⁶⁰ The pandemic may also be a time to reimagine and strengthen community engagement by creating the opportunity for

bidirectional knowledge exchange and ensuring accessibility through more opportunities for remote engagement. Institutions may be willing to be more collaborative by addressing pressing community needs, providing in-kind resources, supporting minority-owned businesses, and practicing authentic community investment, such as directly funding organizations that support community-engaged research. At the federal level, increased consideration could be given to communities of color in funding public-private partnerships.⁶⁹ National research agencies such as the NIH could require community and stakeholder engagement in

funded initiatives and increase funding infrastructure for community-engaged research.⁵⁷

Community-engaged research is an important strategy for addressing inequities in the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond. However, while it can help address some of the downstream health outcomes, partnerships need to advocate for solutions to the longstanding factors contributing to structural racism and health inequities.⁵⁵

Reference Guide: COVID-19 Testing Technologies Overview*

Testing for COVID-19 is an important part of slowing its spread. Testing for COVID-19 can also help people make the right choices to protect themselves and their communities. Because of the challenges posed by the virus, testing methods are constantly evolving as we gather more data. Throughout this fluid test development process, there is an ongoing need for accurate, fast, and readily accessible testing on a global scale.⁹⁹

Accurate Testing

Accurate or reliable tests are tests that detect what they are supposed to detect. An accurate diagnostic test for COVID-19 will correctly identify people who have an infection due to SARS-CoV-2. Test accuracy depends on the type of testing technology used (described below in the section, Types of Tests). The timing for when people take a test is also a factor in its accuracy. When a test fails to detect the virus, that is called a “false negative.” Even accurate tests may result in false-negative results. False negatives are more likely to occur early in an infection (e.g., the time between someone’s exposure and when they develop symptoms) or very late into an infection (e.g., after symptoms have started to lessen). The process of sample collection, the type of sample collected, and the process for performing a test also affects its accuracy.

Fast Testing

Alongside accuracy, there is a great need for fast testing. Once someone has taken a test, they need to get their results back within a reasonable amount of time to make the right decisions on whether to quarantine or self-isolate. The sooner a result is available, the sooner contact tracing can begin. Contact tracing is the process of identifying people who may have been in contact with the person testing positive and letting them know to quarantine or monitor for symptoms. This is described in more detail in the section on Three Typical Uses of COVID-19 Tests.

Readily Accessible Testing

Readily accessible testing means that people can find a place to get tested that is close and convenient to their location. It should also be affordable and safe to access. For communities greatly impacted by COVID-19, accessible testing is critical to slowing and ultimately stopping the spread of the virus. The acceptance of testing is also important to its use in communities. Just because testing is available does not mean people will take advantage of it. Many factors affect the accessibility and acceptance of testing, including cultural and ethical considerations, testing locations, social and economic costs, contact tracing capacity, methods of communication and messaging, and the trustworthiness of sources of information.

*The COVID-19 Testing Technologies Overview is an updated version of content that first appeared in the February 2021 Data Profile.

COVID-19 TESTS AND TESTING APPLICATIONS

Below are three categories of tests¹⁰⁰ the FDA has authorized for emergency use during the COVID-19 pandemic and the three ways these tests are used to help slow or stop the spread of the virus.

Types of Tests

- **Molecular tests**, also known as PCR tests, look for the presence of the viral genetic material in samples taken from the body. These tests work by amplifying regions of the virus genetic material, which is usually present in very low amounts, so it can be detected by the testing instrument. The more virus is present, the easier it is to detect. Depending on the specific test, samples can be run one at a time or can be batched and run hundreds at a time. In some cases, results might be available as quickly as 15 minutes or may take 1 to 2 days to return. The sample used for this type of test is usually a swab that is taken from the respiratory tract (e.g., nose, throat, or saliva).
- **Antigen tests** detect viral proteins (rather than the virus's genetic material) in a sample that is usually collected from the nasal cavity, throat, or saliva. The word "antigen" comes from "antibody generating," meaning these are substances that cause an immune response in the body. Viral proteins are usually only present during the most active part of an infection and, therefore, have a shorter window than viral genetic material in which they will be positive. As a result, antigen tests are less sensitive, meaning they will have higher rates of false-negative results. These tests, which can have results in as soon as 15 minutes, can be used to quickly screen people where they live or work, assuming appropriate testing strategies are followed, as recommended by the CDC.¹⁰¹
- **Serology tests** detect the antibodies the immune system generates in response to a SARS-CoV-2 infection. Since it takes the body days or weeks to generate this response, serology tests are primarily used to determine if someone had COVID-19 in the recent or remote past. These tests, unlike molecular and antigen tests, are performed with blood samples. Processing these tests can take anywhere from 30 minutes to several hours. While the presence of antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 may suggest immunity, it is unknown how long such antibodies remain in the blood after infection. It is also unknown how effective these antibodies are for any given individual in preventing subsequent infections. The reliability of the results also depends on the amount of antibodies present in the body. In other words, serology tests may help identify past infections, but they should not be used as an indication of active infection or immunity against reinfection. The best use for serology tests is the surveillance of a population and not to guide medical decisions for any one individual (described in the section, Three Typical Uses of COVID-19 Tests).

Three Typical Uses of COVID-19 Tests

- **Diagnostic tests** help determine whether COVID-19 is present in someone suspected of having it. Such tests are performed in people who have symptoms or are at high risk of having COVID-19 based on their exposures. Results from diagnostic tests are used to help guide treatment for that person, to guide quarantine decisions for that person, or to offer advice to close contacts (contact tracing). Diagnostic tests may be either a molecular laboratory test (i.e., PCR test) or an antigen test. (See the preceding section for details on these types of tests.)
- **Screening tests** are used to screen a large group of people who may or may not be symptomatic. For example, screening tests may be used on a college campus to identify students who may be positive for SARS-CoV-2 (sometimes without even realizing it). Other settings where screening is performed include nursing

homes, healthcare environments such as hospitals, or other places where essential workers are employed. A variety of molecular or antigen tests are used for screening purposes.

- **Surveillance tests** are used for monitoring COVID-19 at the population or community level. They can be used to inform community and regional policies. Surveillance tests are not used to make decisions about individuals such as quarantining or seeking treatment. Serology testing is often used for surveillance (described in the section, Types of Tests). However, molecular tests can also be used to evaluate samples that are pooled from many people, such as in wastewater. Wastewater surveillance can also help monitor communities at a broad level at less cost. It can also be used to monitor organizations such as schools, LTC facilities, and correctional facilities.¹²

Table 2: Types of COVID-19 Tests

Test Type	Purpose	Component Detected	Sample needed	Testing Location	Analysis Time	Other associated terms	Considerations
Molecular	Identifies active infections; used for diagnosis	Viral RNA	Naso-pharyngeal, nasal or throat swab, saliva	POC or laboratory	Can be as fast as 30 to 60 minutes, but more accurate laboratory tests can take several hours	Diagnostic test, nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT), PCR test, LAMP, isothermal amplification	High sensitivity and specificity with lower probability of false negatives or false positives, but potential delays if sending to a laboratory for processing
Antigen	Identifies active infections; used for diagnosis or screening	Viral proteins	Naso-pharyngeal, saliva	POC	15 to 30 minutes	Rapid diagnostic	Rapid results, ideal for on-site screening, but generally lower sensitivity means that some infections may be missed <i>Please follow testing guidelines recommended by the CDC.</i>
Serology	Identifies past infections; used for surveillance	Human antibodies	Blood	POC or laboratory	Can be as fast as 15 to 30 minutes, but more accurate laboratory tests can take several hours	Antibody test, blood test	Reliability of the result depends on prevalence, and the protective effect of antibodies is still unknown

Modified from: Schneider M, Dentzer S, Sheehan S, et al. From Development to Market: Understanding COVID-19 Testing and its Challenges. Robert J. Margolis Center for Health Policy; 2020.

Reference Guide: COVID-19 Vaccines Overview

In a public health emergency, the FDA can use the Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) authority¹⁰² to make responding to the problem easier and quicker. Once the seriousness of COVID-19 was understood, the need for a vaccine became apparent. The following three vaccine brands were authorized for emergency use in the United States during the COVID-19 pandemic, and one has since been approved by the FDA.¹⁰³

- The **Pfizer-BioNTech** vaccine requires two shots in the muscle of the upper arm. The shots are given three weeks (21 days) apart.¹⁰⁴ This vaccine has been authorized for use in people 5 years and older and fully approved for individuals 16 years and older. Those who have received the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine are considered fully vaccinated two weeks after their second shot.

In clinical trials, the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine was 95 percent effective at preventing infection with SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19. It was shown to be highly effective among people with underlying medical conditions and in a range of age, sex, race, and ethnicity categories.

- The **Moderna** vaccine requires two shots in the muscle of the upper arm.¹⁰⁵ The shots are given four weeks (28 days) apart and have been authorized for use in people 18 years and older. Those who have received the Moderna vaccine are considered fully vaccinated two weeks after their second shot.

In clinical trials, the Moderna vaccine was 94 percent effective at preventing infection with SARS-CoV-2, the virus that causes COVID-19. It was shown to be highly effective among people with underlying medical conditions and in a range of age, sex, race, and ethnicity categories.

- **Johnson & Johnson's (J&J) Janssen** COVID-19 vaccine requires one shot in the muscle of the upper arm.¹⁰⁵ It has been authorized in use for people 18 years and older. Those who have received the vaccine are considered fully vaccinated two weeks after getting the shot.

For all three vaccines, mild side effects, such as pain at the vaccination site, headache, and fever, are common within a day or two and are normal signs of an immune response taking place in the body.

HOW THEY WORK

Each of the COVID-19 vaccines prepares the immune system to protect us against the virus that causes COVID-19, without us having to get sick. Within a few weeks of vaccination, the body produces “memory” cells called T lymphocytes and B lymphocytes¹⁰³ that know how to fight off the virus. How the vaccine creates this response depends on if it is an mRNA vaccine, like the Moderna and Pfizer vaccines, or a viral vector vaccine, like the Johnson & Johnson vaccine.

- **Messenger RNA vaccines**, like the Moderna and Pfizer vaccines, were some of the first COVID-19 vaccines authorized for use in the United States.¹⁰⁶ The technology is relatively new but has been studied before for treating influenza, Zika, and rabies. Instead of putting a weakened or inactivated germ into our bodies, like most vaccines, mRNA vaccines teach cells how to make the harmless S protein found on the spiky, crown-like surface of the coronavirus.¹⁰⁷ This cannot infect the patient with coronavirus, but it does trigger an immune response.¹⁰⁶ Then the mRNA breaks down. It does not affect or interact with our DNA, as it never enters the nucleus of the cell where our DNA is kept.

By injecting COVID-19 mRNA vaccines into the muscle of the upper arm, muscle cells are able to use the mRNA’s “instructions” to produce the protein piece.¹⁰⁶ The protein piece is displayed on the surface of the cell. Then the body responds to the unfamiliar protein by producing an immune response and making T cells and antibodies that recognize the protein.¹⁰³ The symptoms often felt after getting a COVID-19 vaccine, like fever, are part of this response.¹⁰⁶ mRNA vaccines like the Pfizer and Moderna vaccines require two doses because the vaccines provoke a weak immune response when given as one dose.¹⁰⁸ Two weeks after the second dose,

however, the immune system is prepared to recognize and fight off the coronavirus if it enters our bodies.¹⁰³

- As the name suggests, **viral vector vaccines** like J&J’s Janssen vaccine use a safe version of a different virus as a vector to deliver instructions to cells.¹⁰⁶ In the case of the J&J and AstraZeneca vaccines (the latter of which has not been authorized for emergency use in the United States but is in use in many other countries), this vaccine uses an adenovirus as the viral vector.^{110,111} Adenoviruses are common, and infection with one causes mild cold-like symptoms. The adenovirus vector injection, however, is harmless; the patient cannot be infected with either the coronavirus or adenovirus, and it does not interact with the cell’s DNA in any way.

The instructions the vector carries teach cells how to build the harmless S protein on the surface of the virus that causes COVID-19, as with mRNA vaccines.¹⁰⁹ The cell displays the spike protein on its surface, our body recognizes the protein as foreign, and our immune system interprets this as an infection and begins activating immune cells and producing antibodies. Common symptoms after vaccination, such as fever, often occur at this point as part of the immune response.

It still takes a little while for the body to build immunity; two weeks after getting a viral vector vaccine, the immune system can recognize the coronavirus and is prepared to fend it off.¹⁰³

- A **protein subunit vaccine** works by only including the part of the virus that best activates your immune system.¹⁰⁷ In the context of COVID-19, it would contain only the harmless S proteins and initiate the same immune response. Currently there is no protein subunit COVID-19 vaccine authorized for emergency use in the United States, but Novavax has one that delivered promising results in phase 3 clinical trials.

Table 3: COVID-19 Vaccines Authorized for Emergency Use in the U.S.¹⁰³⁻¹⁰⁷

Vaccine	Vaccine type	Who is eligible	How many shots	When are you fully vaccinated	Efficacy*
Pfizer-BioNTech	mRNA	5 and older	2	2 weeks after second dose	95%
Moderna	mRNA	18 and older	2	2 weeks after second dose	94.1%
Johnson & Johnson’s Janssen	Viral vector	18 and older	1	2 weeks after shot	66.3%

*Efficacy refers to effectiveness at preventing laboratory-confirmed infection.

Glossary

GLOSSARY OF COVID-19 TERMS

Antibody—A blood protein the body produces to combat viruses and bacteria. It is also known as an immunoglobulin.

Antigen—Any substance that causes your immune system to produce antibodies against it.

Asymptomatic—When a person is not showing symptoms of a sickness. The person may have a virus but still show no symptoms, or a person may be recovering and their symptoms have gone away.

Close contact—Occurs when someone has come within six feet of an individual with COVID-19 for a total of 15 minutes over a 24-hour period. The 15-minute exposure can be made up of shorter exposures (for example, three separate five-minute exposures for a total 15 minutes).

Contact tracing, associated case investigation—A process for identifying people who come into contact with an infectious disease and following up with them. Contact tracing is an important aspect of stopping the spread of a virus. Also called “associated case investigation.”

COVID-19 vs. SARS-Cov-2—Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is the name of the virus that causes the coronavirus disease (COVID-19). While the virus and the disease it causes are often used to mean the same thing, not everyone who has the virus will develop the disease. While this report refers to testing for COVID-19, tests are actually run for the virus that causes the disease.

Genomic epidemiology for SARS-Cov-2—The process of sequencing the genetic material of SARS-CoV-2 virus samples to better understand the source and nature of an outbreak, as well as to monitor communities for new variants of the virus.

Immunity—The body’s ability to protect itself from infection.

Immunoglobulins—A protein used by the immune system to find and get rid of harmful viruses and bacteria. Also called an antibody.

Infection—Sickness caused by a virus, bacteria, parasites, or other microorganisms.

Isolation—Keeping someone who has or may have COVID-19, or who has tested positive for COVID-19 but has no symptoms, away from others.

Morbidity—The rate of disease in a population.

Mortality—The rate of death, especially on a large scale.

Point-of-care—A test done entirely at the time and place of patient care, such as at the doctor’s office.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing—One of the most common ways of testing for COVID-19. A PCR is a diagnostic test that detects the virus’s genetic material.

Personal protective equipment (PPE)—Equipment that workers can use to protect themselves from dangers. In the case of COVID-19, PPE includes gloves, masks, face shields, goggles, gowns, or coveralls.

Sensitivity and specificity—In diagnostic testing, sensitivity is the ability of a test to correctly identify those with the disease. This is also known as the “true positive rate.” Specificity is the ability of the test to correctly identify those without the disease, which is also known as the “true negative rate.”

Quarantine—Keeping someone who has had close contact with someone with COVID-19 away from others, especially away from those who may be at risk of getting very sick from the virus. The CDC recommends staying home for 14 days after the last contact.

Viral transmission—The process by which a virus spreads from person to person.

GLOSSARY OF OTHER TERMS

Accessibility—The quality of being able to be reached, obtained, or understood.

Allocate—To distribute, such as goods or resources, for a particular purpose.

Auxiliary—Providing supplementary or additional help and support.

Barrier—A roadblock or obstacle in the way of something.

Burnout—Physical or mental collapse caused by overwork or stress.

Community health worker—A member of a community who is chosen by community members or organizations to provide basic health and medical care within their community, and is capable of providing preventive, promotional, and rehabilitation care to that community.

Correctional facility—A place where people are kept after being arrested for a crime. This includes jails, prisons, and juvenile detention centers.

Congregant residence—A group housing arrangement with more than 8 people living and sleeping in one building. Examples include dormitories, correctional facilities, nursing homes, and senior housing.

Community-based—An activity or process that takes place locally, organized by leaders or members of the community.

Consolidation—The action or process of combining a number of things into a single more effective or coherent whole.

Disaggregate—To separate something into its component parts.

Equitable – Fair and impartial.

Extracurricular – An activity at a school or college pursued in addition to the normal course of study.

Disparity—A great difference. In this Data Profile, we are talking about the differences between outcomes for people from different communities.

Demographics—Characteristics of people such as age, race, ethnicity, gender, income, and employment.

Disproportionate—Too large or too small in comparison with something else.

Dissemination—Spreading information .

Federally qualified health centers—Healthcare clinics that get help from the government to serve communities that have fewer resources.

Implement—To put a decision into effect.

Indigenous people—People who are originally from a country or place. In the United States, Indigenous peoples or communities refers to American Indians, Native Alaskans, and Native Hawaiians.

Infrastructure—The basic physical and organizational structures and facilities needed for the operation of a society or enterprise.

Innovation—The process of creating new things.

Interscholastic—Between multiple schools.

Intervention—An action taken, often to improve a situation or a health problem.

Leverage—To use something to maximum advantage.

Linguistic—Relating to language.

Mitigate—To make something less severe.

Predominantly—Mainly; for the most part.

Preventative—Describes actions taken in order to avoid harm or illness.

Uptake—The use of something that is available.

Social determinants of health—The conditions and the environments in which people are born, live, learn, work, play, worship, and age that affect their health and wellbeing.

Socioeconomic—Related to social or financial/income factors.

Sovereignty—The supreme authority within a territory.

Standardize—To cause something to conform to a standard.

Structural racism, systemic racism, institutional racism—Racism that is inherent to an organization's structure.

Telehealth—The provision of healthcare remotely by means of telecommunications technology.

Vulnerable—Able to be harmed or hurt.

Vulnerability Index—A measure of the exposure of a population to some hazard. Typically, the index is a composite of multiple quantitative indicators that via some formula, delivers a single numerical result.

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Second COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy (EA-2) 2021 Agenda At-A-Glance*

Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations

DAY 1: WEDNESDAY, NOVEMBER 17, 2021, 12:00 – 5:00PM ET

12:00–12:05	Welcome – Overview of the Annual EA Series Micky Cohen-Wolkowicz, MD, PhD, Co-PI, RADx-UP CDCC, Duke					
12:05–12:15	Attendee-to-Attendee Greetings and Centering					
12:15–1:00	Land Acknowledgment, Introduction of 1st Keynote Cherry Maynor Beasley, PhD, MS, FAAN, Associate Dean of Health Sciences, McKenzie-Elliott School of Nursing, UNCP DAY 1 NIH OPENING KEYNOTE ADDRESS Linda Burhansstipanov, MSPH, PhD, Society for Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science					
1:00–1:10	Overview of EA-2 – Building Infrastructures for Equitable Testing and Vaccinations Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH, Equity EA Lead, Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine					
1:10–1:15	Break					
1:15–2:15	Concurrent Breakout Session Period I					
	Theme 1: COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing Clemens Hong, MD, MPH	Theme 2: Data Sharing Equity Raynald Samoa, MD	Theme 3: Establishing Communication Frameworks Irene De Barraicua	Theme 4: Pandemic Preparedness Janice Lucas, MA	Theme 5: Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small Hakeem Adeniyi, MD Virginia Hedrick, MPH	Theme 6: Strengthening Multi Sector Partnerships Abeni Bloodworth Deliana Garcia, MA Caleb King Somava Saha MD, MS
2:15–2:20	Break					
2:20–3:20	Concurrent Breakout Session Period 2					
	Theme 1: COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing Becky Smith, PhD, MS, DVM	Theme 2: Data Sharing Equity Stella Yi, MPH, PhD	Theme 3: Establishing Communication Frameworks Brian Southwell, PhD	Theme 4: Pandemic Preparedness Julie Pryde, MPH, MSW, LMSW, CPHA Awais Vaid, MD, MPH	Theme 5: Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small Kenneth Fox, MD	Theme 6: Strengthening Multi Sector Partnerships Aziza Lucas Wright, MEd
3:20–3:35	Break					
3:35–4:05	Reporters Summarize the Six Breakout Sessions					
4:05–4:45	Introduction of Keynote Warren Kibbe, PhD, Co-PI, RADx-UP CDCC, Duke DAY 1 CLOSING KEYNOTE ADDRESS – NATIONAL REFLECTION ON THE DAY'S DISCUSSIONS Patti Brennan, RN, PhD, Director, National Library of Medicine					
4:45–4:55	Instructions + Attendee-to-Attendee Closure					
4:55–5:00	Closing Remarks and Instructions for Day 2 Renee Leverty, MA, RADx-UP CDCC Co-Lead, Duke					

*Please note that exact speakers and titles may have changed since the production of the Data Profile.

Second COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy (EA-2) 2021 Agenda At-A-Glance*

Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations

DAY 2: THURSDAY, NOVEMBER 18, 2021, 12:00 – 3:00PM ET

12:00–12:05	Welcome, Purpose of the Day Krista Perreira, PhD, RADx-UP CDCC Community Engagement Co-Lead and NC CEAL Role, UNC						
12:05–12:15	Attendee-to-Attendee Greetings and Centering						
12:15–12:40	Introduction of Keynote Giselle Corbie, MD, MSc, Co-PI, RADx-UP CDCC, UNC DAY 2 OPENING RECORDED KEYNOTE ADDRESS Marcella Nunez-Smith, MD, MHS, C.N.H. Long Professor, Yale University; Senior Advisor, White House COVID-19 Response Team; Chair, Presidential COVID-19 Health Equity Task Force						
12:40–12:45	Instructions for the Roundtable Discussion Katie Brandert, MPH, Director, Great Plains Leadership Institute, UNMC						
12:45–1:30	Virtual Roundtable Discussions <table border="1" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="background-color: #0056b3; color: white;">Theme 1: COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing</td> <td style="background-color: #4a90e2; color: white;">Theme 2: Data Sharing Equity</td> <td style="background-color: #7ed321; color: white;">Theme 3: Establishing Communication Frameworks</td> <td style="background-color: #00a69a; color: white;">Theme 4: Pandemic Preparedness</td> <td style="background-color: #34495e; color: white;">Theme 5: Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small</td> <td style="background-color: #e67e22; color: white;">Theme 6: Strengthening Multi Sector Partnerships</td> </tr> </table>	Theme 1: COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing	Theme 2: Data Sharing Equity	Theme 3: Establishing Communication Frameworks	Theme 4: Pandemic Preparedness	Theme 5: Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small	Theme 6: Strengthening Multi Sector Partnerships
Theme 1: COVID 19 Surge and Routine Testing	Theme 2: Data Sharing Equity	Theme 3: Establishing Communication Frameworks	Theme 4: Pandemic Preparedness	Theme 5: Addressing Testing and Vaccine Policies Big and Small	Theme 6: Strengthening Multi Sector Partnerships		
1:30–1:45	Break						
1:45–2:05	Reporters Summarize the Roundtable Discussions						
2:05–2:40	Introduction of Keynote Alan Richmond, MSW, RADx-UP CDCC Community Engagement Co-Lead and NC CEAL Co-PI, CCPH DAY 2 CLOSING KEYNOTE ADDRESS – NATIONAL REFLECTION ON THE DAY'S DISCUSSIONS Rev. Dr. Kendrick E. Curry, PhD, MDiv, Pennsylvania Avenue Baptist Church Senior Pastor, Black Coalition Against COVID-19 Community Leader						
2:40–2:55	Attendee-to-Attendee Closure						
2:55–3:00	Closing Remarks Lori Carter-Edwards, PhD, MPH, Equity EA Lead, Kaiser Permanente Bernard J. Tyson School of Medicine						

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